

IS THERE A HYBRID EFFECT IN TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE FAILURE OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES?

Michael R. Wisnom

Bristol Composite Institute, University of Bristol

IMPERIAL

The Composites Centre

for research, modelling, testing and training in advanced composites

Bristol Composites Institute

HYBRID EFFECT

- Can be defined as an increase in failure strain in a hybrid composite compared with when tested on its own
- Reports of hybrid effects from the early days of composites generated much debate, e.g. Hayashi, 1972

- Low extension (LE) fibre e.g. carbon
- High extension (HE) fibre e.g. glass
- Deviation from Rule of Mixtures

Swolfs, 2014

NEED FOR A GOOD BASELINE

- Testing of composites is very challenging
- Failures often occur prematurely at grips
- Compression testing is particularly difficult
- Makes it hard to accurately compare strengths
- Reliable baseline failure strains are crucial for proper assessment of hybrid effects

OUTLINE

- Obtaining a good baseline
- Hybrid effects in tension
 - UD glass/carbon
 - UD high modulus/high strength carbon
 - QI glass/carbon
- Hybrid effects in compression
 - UD high strength carbon / S-glass
 - UD high modulus/high strength carbon

AN ACCURATE SIMPLE TENSILE TEST

- Sandwich specimen eliminates stress concentration
- Strain in carbon LOWER at tab
- Eliminates grip failures

Czél, Jalalvand, Wisnom, 2016

CONSISTENT TENSILE FAILURES

- Gauge section failure followed by delamination
- Much higher failure strain, lower variability
- E.g. 1.86% vs. 1.5% strain for TR30 carbon/epoxy
- Gauge section failure even without end-tabs

SANDWICH BEAM COMPRESSION TEST

- Four-point bending
- Hybrid compression skin
- Carbon tension skin
- Wood or PMMA core
- Large rollers avoid local failures
- Strain gradient effect?

Wu & Wisnom, 2023

VALIDATION OF TEST

- IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy skins, $t = 0.5$ mm
- Little effect of strain gradient above 10 mm thickness
- 1.36% strain - 14% higher than 1.19% in direct compression

(Thomson et al, 2019)

Wu & Wisnom, 2023

HYBRID TENSION TESTS

- Skyflex TR30 high strength carbon/epoxy (0.029 mm)
- Hexcel S2 glass/epoxy plies (0.155 mm) either side

- 3 and 4 ply specimens delaminated with clear load drop
- 1 and 2 ply specimens exhibited pseudo-ductile behaviour

Wisnom et al, 2016

DEFINITION OF FAILURE STRAIN

- Thick specimens: strain at load drop
- Thin specimens: knee point in stress-strain curve
- Corresponds to point of establishment of ply fragmentation
- All results corrected for thermal strains

HYBRID EFFECT IN GLASS / CARBON

- 3 and 4 carbon plies similar, close to expected fibre strain
- 1.86% baseline cf 1.5% with conventional test
- 20% increase in strain to 2.2% for single ply case
- Due to restriction on forming critical cluster

— Baseline strain from delaminating hybrids

Wisnom et al, 2016

HYBRID EFFECT IN ALL CARBON LAMINATES

- Carbon /carbon hybrids also show hybrid effect
- Ultra high modulus XN80 (0.047 mm ply t)
- T1000 intermediate modulus (0.032 mm ply t)
- $[T1000_2/XN80_2/T1000_2]$ versus $[T1000_1/XN80_1/T1000_1]_2$
- ~30% higher than datasheet laminate failure strain of 0.31%
- 6% increase in knee point strain for single XN80 ply

Czél, Jalalvand, Wisnom, Czigány 2017

QUASI-ISOTROPIC PSEUDO-DUCTILE HYBRIDS

- $[Q]_{G60/Q}C60]_s$ tested in 0, 60 and -60 directions
- 13% higher strain when loaded in 0° direction
- Due to higher stiffness of adjacent 0° glass ply
- Can be correlated with stress concentrations in adjacent plies (Idarraga et al, 2025)

■ S2-Glass – 0.15 mm
■ T300 Carbon – 0.03 mm

Fotouhi, Jalalvand, Wisnom, 2017

COMPRESSIVE FAILURE OF CARBON/GLASS HYBRIDS

- High strength TC33 carbon, 95 GPa, 0.03 mm
- S-glass, 45 GPa, 0.155 mm ply thickness
- Tested in 4-point bending
- Sudden failures with kink bands
- Large hybrid effect - 54% increase in strain
- Similar stresses – instability more related to stress than strain

Specimen configuration	Compressive failure strain (%) CV(%)	Laminate failure stress (MPa)
SG/TC33 ₁ /SG	2.609 (8)	1271
SG/TC33 ₂ /SG	2.234 (8)	1232
SG/TC33 ₁₆ /SG	1.691 (6)	1121

stress than strain

Tongloet, 2025

HIGH MODULUS CARBON / GLASS HYBRIDS

Direct compression

Suwarda et al., 2025

- M55J high modulus PAN, ply $t=0.03$ mm, 240 GPa
- S-glass, $t=0.155$ mm, 45 GPa
- 17 repeats with single glass ply between each carbon sublaminates
- Thickness 3.31 to 4.35 mm

Layup 1
S-glass
M55J
S-glass

Layup 2
S-glass
M55J
M55J
S-glass

Layup 3
S-glass
M55J
M55J
M55J
S-glass

S-GLASS / HIGH MODULUS CARBON HYBRID EFFECT

- Pseudo-ductile response with fragmentation
- Controlled by fibre failure not shear instability
- Final failure by delamination
- Knee point at 0.5% for all cases
- No hybrid effect?

S-GLASS / HIGH MODULUS CARBON HYBRID EFFECT

- Knee point at $\sim 0.5\%$ for all cases
- But failure strain of monolithic M55J composite reported $\sim 0.31\%$ (Montagnier & Hochard, 2004)
- Hybrid effect – fibre failure is delayed by support from Glass
- But fragmentation still occurs at similar strains

HIGH MODULUS / HIGH STRENGTH CARBON HYBRIDS

34-700/TP415 60 gsm
 HR40/TP415

Unidirectional laminates

Fibre type	Fibre tensile modulus (GPa)
34-700	234
HR40	390

Sandwich 4 point bending test

Tongloet et al, 2025

HIGH MODULUS / HIGH STRENGTH CARBON HYBRIDS

- No fragmentation or pseudo-ductility
- All failures show kink bands
- HR40 failure strain nearly doubled
- Due to support from 34-700
- Hybrid effect
- Fibre failure initiates by instability
- Before fibre fracture, failure transitions to composite instability

IS THERE A HYBRID EFFECT?

- Yes - significant effects in tension and compression
- But - need good baseline for valid comparison
- Tension – up to 20% increase in strain for thin plies
- Due to restriction in forming critical cluster
- Compression – large increases in failure strain when failure by composite shear instability (Std. Mod. C/G)
- Fibre failure instability delayed (HM C) but similar fragmentation strain
- Hybrid effects in compression due to support against instability

REFERENCES

1. Czél, G., M. Jalalvand, and M.R. Wisnom, *Hybrid specimens eliminating stress concentrations in tensile and compressive testing of unidirectional composites*. Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2016. **91**: p. 436-447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.07.021>
2. Czél, G., et al., *Design and characterisation of high performance, pseudo-ductile all-carbon/epoxy unidirectional hybrid composites*. Composites Part B-Engineering, 2017. **111**: p. 348-356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.11.049>
3. Fotouhi, M., M. Jalalvand, and M.R. Wisnom, *High performance quasi-isotropic thin-ply carbon/glass hybrid composites with pseudo-ductile behaviour in all fibre orientations*. Composites Science and Technology, 2017. **152**: p. 101-110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2017.08.024>
4. Hayashi T, K.K., Yamazaki A, Kihira M, *Development of new material properties by hybrid composition*. 2nd report. Fukugo Zairyo (Composite Materials) 1972. **1**: p. 21-25.
5. Idarraga G, J. Acosta, M. Jalalvand, J. Meza and M. R. Wisnom, *Hybrid Effect in Multi-directional Carbon/Glass Composites*, Composites Science and Technology, 2025. p. 111285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2025.111285>
6. Suwarta, P., et al., *Pseudo-ductile compressive behaviour of unidirectional thin-ply carbon /glass fibre-epoxy hybrid composites*. Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2025. **195**:108877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2025.108877>
7. Swolfs, Y., L. Gorbatikh, and I. Verpoest, *Fibre hybridisation in polymer composites: A review*. Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2014. **67**: p. 181-200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.08.027>
8. Tongloet, A., Wisnom, M.R., Wu, X., Argyropoulos, A., Cugnoni, J., Michaud, V., *Compressive behaviour of high modulus/high strength thin-ply carbon fibre hybrid composites*. To be published, 2025.
9. Tongloet, A, *Compressive Behaviour of Longitudinal Hybrid Composites*, PhD thesis, 2025. University of Bristol.
10. Wisnom, M.R., et al., *Hybrid effects in thin ply carbon/glass unidirectional laminates: Accurate experimental determination and prediction*. Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2016. **88**: p. 131-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.04.014>
11. Wu, X. and M.R. Wisnom, *Compressive failure strain of unidirectional carbon fibre composites from bending tests*. Composite Structures, 2023. **304**: p. 116467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.116467>

Next COMP

Next Generation
Fibre-Reinforced Composites

<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

I would like to acknowledge funding which supported this work from the UK Research and Innovation - EPSRC Programme Grant; Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites: A Full Scale Redesign for Compression (EP/T011653/1)

A collaboration between Imperial College London and University of Bristol

IMPERIAL

